

Some Fungicidal 3-Aryl/Aryloxymethyl-4-Aryl-5-Mercapto-1,2,4-Triazoles and Bis-(3-Aryloxymethyl-4-Aryl-1,2,4-Triazol-5-yl)-Methylene/Ethylene Disulphides

S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHEL*

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

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Eighteen 3-aryl/aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and twenty bis-(8-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-methylene/ethylene disulphides have been prepared. All the compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activity against '*A. flavus*' and '*A. niger*' and were found to be antifungal.

3-AMINO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE (Amizole) is a commercial herbicide. Several 1,2,4- and 1,3,4-triazoles and compounds containing triazole ring have been found to have bactericidal^{1,2}, fungicidal^{3,4}, insecticidal^{5,6} and pesticidal^{7,8} properties. With this in view, some title 1,2,4-triazoles have been prepared.

Heterocyclic sulphides have been reported to possess antitubercular, anticancer and antifungal⁹ activities. The pesticidal screening results of bis-(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) alkanes have revealed that as the number of methylene group increased, activity increased in some respects¹⁰. A comparative study of pesticidal activity of mercapto compounds and their sulphides has shown that sulphides are relatively more active than parent mercapto compounds¹¹. Hence, the title disulphides have also been prepared.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aryl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of L. Conti¹².

3-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles¹³ :

Aryl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01M) and aryl isothiocyanate (0.012M) were dissolved in 8% aqueous sodium hydroxide (17.5 ml) and the mixture refluxed gently for five hours. It was poured into a large excess of water, stirred and then filtered. The filtrate was acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The triazoles thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

Bis-(3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-methylene/ethylene disulphides :

To an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 3-aryloxy-methyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01M), fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) and methylene/ethylene dichloride (0.005M) were added. The contents were refluxed for four hours, cooled and then poured into water. The solid separated was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 1—3-ARYL/ARYLOXYMETHYL-4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES

Compound number	Name	M.P. °C	Yield (%)
1. ^a	3-(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	107	95
2.	3-(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	168	60
3.	3-(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	156	85
4.	3-(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	122	75
5.	3-(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	102	72
6. ^b	3-(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy-methyl)-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	111	84
7.	3-(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	106	80
8.	3-(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	110	82
9.	3-(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	136	72
10.	3-(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy-methyl)-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	117	74
11. ^c	3-Benzyl-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	157	85
12.	3-Benzyl-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	48	78
13.	3-Benzyl-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	53	80
14. ^d	3- α -Naphthylmethyl-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	123	88
15.	3- α -Naphthylmethyl-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	120	80

* Lecturer, Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur.

(Table 1 Contd.)

16.	3- α -Naphthylmethyl-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	129	87
17.	3- α -Naphthylmethyl-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	84.75	75
18.	3- α -Naphthylmethyl-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole	91	80

All the compounds showed consistent nitrogen analysis.

IR Spectral data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm^{-1}

a. 3325($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{N}}-\overset{|}{\text{H}}$) ; 1155($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{S}}$) ; 1050, 1250($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$) ; 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring) and 660 (C-Cl).

b. 3320($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{N}}-\overset{|}{\text{H}}$) ; 1175($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{S}}$) ; 1050, 1260($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$) and 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring).

c. 3325($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{N}}-\overset{|}{\text{H}}$) ; 1170($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{S}}$) and 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring).

d. 3320($\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{N}}-\overset{|}{\text{H}}$) ; (1170- $\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{S}}$) ; 1060, 1265($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$), 1580 (Aromatic ring further conjugated) and 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring).

(Table 2 Contd.)

34.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	78	71
35. ^h	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	98	60
36.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	76	65
37.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	45	62
38.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	52	70

All the compounds showed consistent nitrogen analysis.

IR Spectral data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm^{-1}

e. 1050, 1250($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$), 650 (C-Cl) and 850 (*p*-disubstituted benzene ring).

f. 1060, 1250($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$) and 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring).

g. 1060, 1255($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$), 720, 750 (monosubstituted benzene ring) and 665 (C-Cl).

h. 1055, 1260($=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{O}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-$), 650(C-Cl) and 800 (*m*-substituted benzene ring).

TABLE 2-Bis(3-ARYLOXYMETHYL)-4-ARYL-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-5-YL)-METHYLENE/ETHYLENE DISULPHIDES

Compound number	Name	M.P. °C	Yield (%)
19.	Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	179	70
20.	Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	150	60
21. ^e	Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	186	65
22.	Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	135	63
23.	Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	190	67
24. ^f	Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	132	75
25.	Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	125	62
26.	Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	137	68
27.	Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	120	65
28.	Bis-[3-(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-methylene disulphide	176	70
29. ^g	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	121	67
30.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	110	59
31.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	115	60
32.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>m</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	96	60
33.	1'',2''-Bis-[3-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)methyl]-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-ethylene disulphide	100	62

Fungicidal activity :

All the compounds of Tables 1 and 2 have been screened for their antifungal activity against '*A. niger*' and '*A. flavus*' by agar plate technique^{14,15} at three different concentrations namely, 1 : 1,000 ; 1 : 10,000 ; 1 : 1,00,000 and were found to be antifungal. Groups substituted at the position 4 (Table 1 and 2) had the following order for the fungicidal activity :

and the groups at the position 3 showed the following order :

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